

A Study on Consumer Attitude towards Eco-Friendly Products in Chennai City

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Dr. K. Shyamala

Assistant Professor, SDNB. Vaishnav College, Chromepet, Chennai

Abstract

Recently, climate change problems have come to the forefront. Climate change is a global challenge. It is a threat to economic stability and social and sustainable human existence. There is no doubt that weather change affects the fundamental requirement for health – safe drinking water, clean air, sufficient green food and secured shelter. This study was conducted in Chennai City, with a sample size 100. Data was collected well-structured questionnaires. Ranking analysis and percentage analysis were used as data analysis tools. The consumers are aware of the eco-friendly products and are having a positive attitude towards eco-friendly products. It was found that the lack of knowledge and not aware of the benefits are barriers for purchasing eco-friendly products. Majority of the respondents buy eco-friendly products for health purpose. So it is time to generate the concept of green marketing to the young generation.

Keywords: Eco-friendly product, Green consumer, Social responsibility, Health care.

Introduction

Green marketing definitions can be a little confused since green marketing can refer to anything from greening stock growth to the actual advertising campaign itself. Going by alternative titles such as sustainable marketing, green advertising, environmental marketing, organic marketing, eco marketing, all of which point to related concepts though reasonably in a more green marketing, specific fashion is actually a way to brand your marketing information in order to capture more of the market by appealing to people’s desire to services and choose products that are better for the atmosphere.

What is green marketing?

Eco-friendly product refers to the process of selling products and services based on their environmental advantages. Such a stock or service may be environmentally favourable in it or produced and packaged in an environmentally friendly route.

The clear opinion of green marketing is that potential customers will view a product or service’s “greenness” as a benefit and base their purchasing decision, respectively. The not-so-obvious assumption of green purchasing is that customers will be willing to pay more for green stocks than they would for a less-green similar alternative product - an assumption.

Evolution of Eco- friendly products

- The green marketing has evolved over this season. The evolution of green shopping had three phases. The first phase was termed as “Ecological” green marketing, and during this period all marketing activities were concerned to help environment problems and give remedies for environmental problems.
- The second phase was “Environmental” green marketing, and the focus shifted on clean technology that involved designing innovative new products, which take care of pollution and waste issues.
- The third period was “Sustainable” green purchasing. It arrived into prominence in the late 1990s and early 2000. This was the conclusion of the term sustainable development which is defined as “meeting the requirements of the present without compromising the efficacy of forthcoming generations to meet their own needs.”

Benefits of Eco- Friendly Products

Companies that improved products and develop new and services with environment inputs in mind give themselves access to new shops, increase their profit sustainability, and enjoy a competitive advantage over the companies which are not concerned for the environment.

Some of the benefits of Eco-friendly products are,

1. It assures sustained long-term increase, along with profitability.
2. It saves money in the long run, though initially, the cost is more.
3. It helps companies market their products and services, keeping the environmental aspects in mind. It helps in reaching the new markets and enjoying a competitive benefit.
4. Most of the employees also feel proud and responsible to be working for an environmentally responsible corporation.

Review of Literature

All around the globe, green marketing had been considered as one of the major trends in modern businesses (Kassaye, 2001; McDaniel and Rylander, 1993; Pujari and Wright, 1996). The concept of green products and green services was dated back in the late 1980s (Nervi, 2008). Since then, to be environment friendly became a trendy characteristic that was being associated with the certain category of products that were limited to the elite, as a general idea about environment friendly products was expensive than conventional products.

Thus, they didn't find their place in everyday shopping habits. But with the increased awareness about the environmental issues, consumers had become more demanding, and they began to pay more attention to the preservation of the environment (Rajpot, 2011; Bukhari, 2011). Environment conscious consumers, also known as green consumers, felt that the environmental protection job should not have left to businesses, government, scientists and environmentalists only. They believed that consumers should have also played a role and should incline more towards pro-environmental purchase behaviour (Beztov, 2012).

Environmental marketing, more commonly known as green marketing or sustainable marketing can be defined as the effort by a company to promote, price, design and distribute products in a manner which promotes environmental protection (Polonsky, 2011). Green marketing has been defined as ‘all activities designed to generate and facilitate any exchanges intended to satisfy human wants or wants such that the satisfaction of these needs and wants occurs, with a minimal detrimental impression on the natural environment’ by Polonsky (2011).

Consumerism can be identified as a movement which originally began as a process which was presented to protect consumers against practices of unethical marketing. Over time this has

extended and become broader. When today's agenda with regards to consumer activism is taken into consideration, it can be observed that protection of the environment is the most vital aspect (Dono et al., 2010). There is a resultant improvement in the concern expressed towards environmental protection leading to “green consumerism” (Eriksson, 2002).

The growth of green marketing and green consumer is “perhaps the biggest opportunity for enterprise and invention the industrial world has ever seen” (Cairncross 1992: 177). A green consumer can be identified to be one who avoids any product which may harm damage to any living organism, cause deterioration of the environment during the process of manufacturing or process of usage, consume a high cost of non-renewable

Energy involves immoral testing on animals or human subjects (Elkington, 1994).

There have been several different factors which are instrumental in promoting green customers to purchase green products. Inclusive research over the years identifies that heightened awareness of green issues; increased the level of information available on environmental sustenance; green posting by corporations; increased concern for the situation; develop in following of green products by social and environmental charities as some factors.

According to the consumer's consciousness about the environment might have an impact on its purchase decisions, but they could also be inspired by the other moderating factors. Research indicated that attitudes were the major predictors of environmental purchase behaviour. On the other hand, about eco-literacy contradictory findings exist in the literature (Schlegelmilch et al., 1996) as Lai (2000) concluded that it was not necessary that all customers who were environmentally aware and conscious would have green purchase behaviour.

These findings were found to be in line with Maloney and Ward (1973), who confirmed the non-existence of linkage between environmental knowledge and ecologically compatible behaviour. Contrarily, it was concluded in some studies that eco-literate people tend to pay premium prices for environment friendly products (Amyx et al. 1994).

Green buying behaviours and intentions were also found to be influenced by the social group's responsiveness and knowledge. Furthermore, Research also stated that the perceived seriousness of the environmental issues and an individual's exposure to the problem had also been associated with the green brand preference (Hassan et al., 2012). Moreover, Behavioural change towards sustainable development driven by the concern for environmental issues proved to last longer than behaviour driven by financial incentives or offers. (Young et al. 2006).

With the growing popularity of green products, many firms began to exploit the green marketing strategies by their fake green claims. Thus, it was found that consumers used to boycott those firms or organization that took advantage of the green movement and falsely claim to have products that were environmentally safe. Thus if companies were not fair in their claims and were just exploiting the green marketing, consumers might become alienate and boycott purchasing from such companies (Cairncross, 1992; Polonsky, 1994).

Furthermore, it was also found that a positive attitude towards environmental issues didn't necessarily translate into environment friendly purchasing behaviour. It was found that the majority of consumers didn't merely purchase products based on their environmental concern; rather, they considered other product attributes while making a purchase decision (Gan, 2008). D'Souza et al., (2006) reported that if green products were of lower quality with high prices, then generally, consumers' perceptions and consumers' purchase intentions were found to be negatively associated.

There was an expectation on behalf of the consumers that the green products offered should have been environmentally safe and there should not have been a need to trade off quality or pay extra prices for such products (Gupta and Ogden, 2009).

Objectives of the study

- To know the consumer attitude for Eco-friendly products.
- To find the consumer's preference to Eco – friendly product.

Hypotheses

- The factors of Consumer attitude do not differ significant.
- There is no significant difference between the factors of an eco-friendly product.

Area of the Study

The study is imprisoned to Chennai City only.

Sample Size

Since the population for the survey are very large, and due to time limitation, a sample size of 100 is taken for the survey.

Sources of Data

Primary Data

Survey method is employed to collect the data from the respondents, and the data are collected.

Secondary data

The secondary data was gathered from magazines, journals, books, articles, research papers and websites.

Research Tools

- Percentage analysis
- Ranking analysis

Sampling Method

The study mainly depends on the Primary data collected through a well-structured Questionnaire distributed to in Chennai alone.

Data Instrument

well-structured Questionnaire

Limitations

- The Research Area was confined to Chennai Only.
- The sample size was only 100
- Respondent's opinion differs from time to time.

Demographic Variable	Classification	No. of respondent	Percentage
Gender	Male	65	65%
	Female	35	35%
Marital Status	Married	88	88%
	Single	12	12%

Age	Below 20	01	01%
	21-30	18	18%
	31-40	47	47%
	41-50	23	23%
	Above 51	12	12%
Education	Higher secondary	01	01%
	Diploma holders	15	15%
	Graduate	60	60%
	Post graduate	10	10%
Status	Professional	14	14%
	Employee	43	43%
	Business	10	10%
	Professional	26	26%
	Homemaker	11	11%
	Retired person	08	08%
	Others	00	02%
Monthly family income	Below 25000	25	25%
	25001-50000	50	50%
	50001-75000	16	16%
	75001-100000	03	03%
	Above 100001	07	07%
Size of the family	5 Members	30	30%
	4 Members	40	40%
	3and below	30	30%

The above table reveals that the majority of the respondents, 65% was male 35% of them are female. A vast majority of the 88% were married, and the remaining 12% of the remaining were single.

The table also shows that the 47% of the consumers belonged to the age group 31-40, 23% of them were in the age group of 41-50, 18% of the respondents from 21-30 age group, 12 were above the age of 51, and 1% of the eco-friendly consumers were below 20 years.

Based on education 60% of the respondents were found to be graduates, 15% of them were Diploma holders, 14% of the respondents were professional degree, 10% of the consumers were post graduates, and 1% of the small group of them are having the education of higher secondary.

The table also found that the employment status of the respondents 43% of them are employee, 26% of them were a profession, 11% of them homemakers, 10% of them businessman, 8% of them retired persons and 2% of them belong to another category.

The table above shows that the respondents 50% are having the monthly family income of Rs.25001-50,000, 25% of the consumers are getting a monthly income of 25,000

16% of them have the income of Rs.50001 -75000, 3% of them have the monthly family income from Rs.75001-100000.7% of them are above income of Rs.100001. The table depicts that the respondents 40% are having the family size of 4 members, 30% of them have family size five, and of the respondents are having a family size of 3 and below.

Sources of Awareness on Eco-friendly Products

S. No	Source of Information	%
1.	Radio	2
2.	Television	17
3.	News paper	5
4.	Outdoor advertisements	15
5.	Product label	18
6.	Websites	31
7.	Word of mouth	12

The table shows that nearly 31% of the respondents believe that websites are major sources of awareness towards eco-friendly products. 18% of the respondents have revealed that Product label advertisement has made them to aware of eco-friendly products. 15% of them found that Out door advertisements are sources of information and 2% & 5% find that newspaper and radio have made them aware of eco-friendly products. 17 and 12% of them find that television and word of mouth have made them know about eco-friendly products.

Consumers' Buying Intention of Eco-Friendly Products

Sl. No	Buying intention	Percentage
1	For serving environment	30%
2	For health factors	49%
3	For the appreciation from others	16%
4	For pressure from someone	04%
5	For I saw many people purchase them	13%

The table reveals that majority, 49% of the respondents buy eco-friendly products for health reasons. 30% of them purchasing eco-friendly products for serving the environment. 16% of them purchasing them for appreciation from others. 13% of them purchase it for that they saw many people purchase them, and 4% of them are buying it for pressure from someone.

One-Sample Statistics and Ranking Analysis for the Factors of the Decision to Purchase Eco-friendly Products

Factors	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-value	Significance	Rank
I always check if the products I buy are environmentally safe	100	3.1626	1.35468	.05664	2.870	.004	4th Rank
I go and search of eco-friendly products if it is not available in one shop.	100	3.4213	1.47332	.06160	6.839	.000	2nd Rank
I take a chance to convince my family members to buy eco-friendly products	100	3.3741	1.33781	.05594	6.688	.000	3rd Rank

I appreciate the package/design of eco-friendly products.	100	2.3024	1.34482	.05623	-12.405	.000	9th Rank
I believe in the information on eco-friendly package.	100	2.4458	1.57993	.06606	-8.389	.000	8th Rank
I pay attention to eco-friendly advertising.	100	2.4965	1.53248	.06408	-7.858	.000	7th Rank
I believe in the eco-friendly advertising.	100	3.4895	1.50826	.06306	7.762	.000	1st Rank
I am ready to pay little extra price for eco-friendly products.	100	2.9423	1.46954	.06144	-.939	.348	5th Rank
Eco-friendly products will not perform as same as normal brands.	100	2.5962	1.69563	.07090	-5.696	.000	6th Rank
Eco-friendly products will not perform as same as normal brands.	100	2.9930	1.29120	.05399	-.130	.897	10th Rank

The above table found that the ranking factors of the eco-friendly products believe in the eco-friendly advertising ranks 1st. The 2nd rank goes and searches for eco-friendly products if it is not available in one shop. The 3rd rank goes to take a chance to convince my family members to buy eco-friendly products. The consumer gives 4th rank always to check if the products I buy are environmentally safe, am ready to pay a little extra price for eco-friendly products Ranks 5th. Eco-friendly products will not perform as same as normal brands rank 6th. I pay attention to eco-friendly advertising, I believe in the information on the eco-friendly package, appreciate the package/design of eco-friendly products — 6th,7th and 8th rank respectively. The 9th and 10th palace goes to I appreciate the package/design of eco-friendly products, have to shift to a greener lifestyle.

Recommendations

- Green marketing is a continuous process that needs constant inputs from the suppliers, government legislations and policies and the people.
- This is required so that the businesses green marketing strategy can be aligned to the target markets and so it can gain a sustainable aggressive advantage.
- It is essential that policies and methods about green products be developed and implemented to guide and help the retailers and consumers towards a green change.
- Businesses should concentrate on centring on developing a green product that has demand from the general public and which also aligns to the company’s core positioning. Moreover, companies should also present efforts in a manner that reduces the risk related to costs.
- In conclusion, creating and achieving a green marketing strategy is not straight forward because it is not only complex but also a relative thought that continuously varies over time.
- The framework that is shown in the current paper is based on the need to explain inconsistencies in attitudes and behaviours that have been revealed in past researches.
- Furthermore the framework also tries to support certain ways to cover the research gap.
- The current study will provide valuable insight to both practitioners and theoreticians who want to understand environmentally conscious individuals.

- Since the success of green products depend on the customers adopting or changing their attitude and behaviour towards such products, it is necessary that green marketers identify all the factors that encourage cooperation.
- Thus the current study will also be of advantage to the green marketers as it aids in developing a marketing strategy that persuades consumers to seek the value of collective gain over self-interest.

Conclusion

It has been observed from the analysis that large population thinks that eco-friendly products are good for the environment and are also healthy for them. Eco-friendly products are good quality, and the performances of these are better than the conventional products. These products are easily available in the market at reasonable charges. While shopping,

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Web Marketing

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